

AMIR TEMUR'S UNIQUE MANAGEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the governance system that Amir Temur the founder of the Timurid dynasty, developed for the prosperity and peace of his state.

The past of our country goes back a long way. If we look at history, dynasties such as Khionids, Kidaris, Ephtals, Khorezmshahs, Samonis, and Timurids have been ruling our country since ancient times. It should be said that among these dynasties, the Timurid dynasty is the state that has been ruling for many years. The main reason for long years of rule is a unique management system.

The founder of the Timurid dynasty, Amir Temur ibn Amir Taragai ibn Amir Barqul, is the ruler who developed a unique management system for the prosperity of the kingdom, prosperity and peace in the state. Based on his own experience, Sahibqiran stated that the ruler should follow the following rules in state management:

1. (with yourself) Council;
1. (with others) Counseling;
3. Decision-making with vigilance and consideration;
4. Be careful; [1.14]

As the head of state, Amir Temur was a far-seeing, patient, and deep-thinking head of state. As he said, when the councilors and members of the council met, he discussed the pros and cons, advantages and disadvantages of the tasks ahead, their implementation and non-proliferation, and consulted with the council.

It is known. The country created by the master occupied a huge area. Managing a huge kingdom, coming to terms with conquered territories is a difficult task. The fact that Amir Timur respected the dignitaries of any country he conquered, paid obeisance to their sayyids, scholars, fuzalo and mashoyikhs, highly respected the nobles and dignitaries of every country. history is a witness that he respects and raises the ranks, opens the door of justice in every country and blocks the path of oppression.

In particular, the following sentences are mentioned in "Tuzuklari Temur":

"May the Sayyids, scholars, sheikhs, virtuous people, dervishes, and hermits of the country who are subject to me be rewarded with suurg, duty and salary. Allow them to give

allowances to the poor and the disabled. They should set daily salaries for the teachers and sheikhs.

Let them allocate funds from the endowment for the graves and mausoleums of saints and religious leaders. Let them provide palos, food and lamps there. I also ordered that after the conquest of each country, they should collect the beggars of that land, provide them with daily food and drink, give them something to do, and let them all be branded. If they continue to beg even after the stamp, they should be sold to distant countries or driven away. Only then, the gado breed will disappear from the country." [2.141-142]

As can be seen from the above, Sahibgiron was generous, a lover of knowledge, and a demanding person who was firm in his decision. Being a far-seeing and deep-thinking person, he was careful not to delay any goals, plans, and decisions he wanted to make. In particular, Sahibqiran himself emphasizes this: "I did not leave today's work for tomorrow. I was gentle when gentleness was needed. When it was time to use firmness, I took firm measures. Don't rush, I didn't rush, I didn't delay urgent work. I did not use a sword when it was possible to combine work with action. [3.135]

Amir Temur, in addition to managing the state, also paid special attention to the prosperity and prosperity of the country. He built mosques, madrassas and gardens. The country's cities were named after the world's most famous cities and flourished. In particular, he managed to turn the capital Samarkand into one of the most beautiful cities in the world and left an indelible mark in history. He ordered to build mosques, madrasahs and houses not only in his kingdom, but also in every city, village, large and small in the conquered territories. He ordered to build hospitals for the sick and appoint doctors to work in them. In addition, the ruler attached special importance to the safety of the population. We can know this from the fact that palaces and courthouses were built in all cities, and guards were appointed by raiyat-u-ziraat.

We know that the immortal and unique structures built during the time of Amir Temur still brighten our lives today. In particular, it is not an exaggeration to say that the wise use of the huge heritage of the architectural ideas created by the genius of Amir Temur in modern Uzbek architecture is one of the responsible tasks for today's masters and architects.

The architectural solutions in buildings such as the "State Museum of the History of the Timurids" in Tashkent, the Imam al-Bukhari memorial complex near Samarkand, among the buildings of the period of independence, built in the traditions of Amir Temur's era, are evidence of the seriousness of this task.

Therefore, studying the ideas and methods that scientifically and theoretically enriched the field of architecture, construction, and urban planning of the Sahibqiran period is the demand of the time. [4.15] Even today, we are enjoying the great treasure of enlightenment left by Amir Temur. It is not wrong to say that the lessons of Amir Temur are especially useful in educating the dedicated youth of our independent country. Even today, the great written legacy left by Sohigiron, the book "Timur's Laws", serves as a program in many ways.

As for the scientific value of "Tuzuklar", the administrative structure of Timur and the Timurid state plays an important role in studying the rules that prevailed in the palace and people's life at that time, and in understanding the nature of the largest state that ruled in

Central Asia. transportation is clear. From this point of view, it would be appropriate if it is thoroughly analyzed and republished in full with the necessary scientific comments. [5. 157]

It is known that during the Shura system, Amir Temur's personality and career were unfairly treated and given a one-sided assessment. After our country gained independence, such prejudices were abolished. Amir Temur's place in world history began to be put into place. The name of Amir Temur has been immortalized in our country. Main streets, squares, schools, etc. in many cities and villages were named after him. In 1995, the International Amir Temur Foundation was established. A statue of Amir Temur was erected in the central squares of Tashkent, Samarkand, Shahrisabz and other cities, in 1996, a museum of the Temur era was established on Amir Temur Avenue in Tashkent, and the Order of "Amir Temur" was established. A two-part feature film, plays, and poetic and prose works were created about Amir Temur. Every year Amir Temur's birthday is widely celebrated in our country. All this shows the attention paid to the memory of the great statesman.

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